

SEQUENCE OF TENSES IN ENGLISH: THEORY AND PRACTICE

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Abstract. *This study explores English verb tenses and the sequence of tenses in reported speech. It examines the three main verb tenses—past, present, and future—and their use in expressing temporal relationships between actions or states. Special attention is given to how verbs change when transforming direct speech into reported speech, including changes in pronouns and temporal adverbs. The research highlights patterns of tense transformation, such as Present → Past, Past → Past Perfect, and Future → Future in the Past, as well as cases where the tense remains unchanged. The study also discusses practical implications for translating English texts into Tajik and emphasizes the importance of mastering tense sequences for accurate communication and comprehension.*

Keywords: *English verb tenses, sequence of tenses, reported speech, direct speech, past, present, future, temporal relations*

ПОСЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬНОСТЬ ВРЕМЁН В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

ИБРАГИМОВА РАНО АБДУШУКУРОВНА

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Аннотация. *Данное исследование посвящено временам английского глагола и последовательности времён в косвенной речи. Рассматриваются три основных времени глагола — прошедшее, настоящее и будущее — и их использование для выражения временных отношений между действиями или состояниями. Особое внимание уделяется изменениям глаголов при преобразовании прямой речи в косвенную, включая изменения местоимений и наречий времени. В работе выделяются закономерности изменения времён, такие как Present → Past, Past → Past Perfect и Future → Future in the Past, а также случаи, когда время глагола остаётся неизменным. Исследование также рассматривает практическое значение этих правил при переводе английских текстов на таджикский язык и подчёркивает важность освоения последовательности времён для точной передачи смысла и правильного понимания текста.*

Ключевые слова: *Времена английского глагола, последовательность времён, косвенная речь, прямая речь, прошедшее, настоящее, будущее, временные отношения*

The verb, as the most complex part of speech, has a wide range of meanings and grammatical relationships, expressed through verb forms, moods, aspects, voices, and tenses. Verb tenses indicate the temporal relationship of an action or state with the moment of speech or with another moment in time. English verbs have three main tenses - past, present, and future.

A key aspect of English grammar is the sequence of tenses in subordinate clauses. The tense of the verb in a subordinate clause depends on the tense of the verb in the main clause. For example, when the main clause verb is in the past tense, demonstrative pronouns and temporal adverbs often change in reported speech (e.g., here → there, now → then, today → that day).

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that the sequence of tenses is one of the most challenging and important topics for English learners. Understanding it is crucial for constructing accurate reported speech, translating literary and academic texts, and developing clear written and spoken communication skills. Analyzing the rules of tense transformation in reported speech provides a deeper understanding of English verb tenses and facilitates their practical use.

The verb, as the most complex part of speech, has a wide range of meanings and grammatical relationships, which are expressed through verb forms, moods, aspects, voices, and tenses. The tense of a verb indicates the temporal relation of an action with the moment of speech or with another moment in speech. A verb has three tenses and is conjugated in various tense forms: past, present, and future [3, p. 287]:

a) Past – an action or state that occurred before the moment of speech. In this regard, we are discussing the past tense of the verb:

1. They were as old as erosions in a fishless desert [7, p. 6]. – Онҳо мисли тарқишҳои биёбони беоб кӯҳна буданд.

b) Present – an action or state that may coincide with the moment of speech. In this case, we refer to the present tense:

I am a boy and I must obey him [7, p. 8]. – Ман ҳанӯз бачаам, бояд ба падарам итоат кунам.

c) Future – an action or state that may occur after the moment of speech. In this case, we refer to the future tense:

I'll be back when I have the sardines [7, p. 16]. – Ман ҳамин ки сардин гирифтаам, бармегардам.

From the above explanation and examples, it is clear that the speaker refers to three types of actions or states:

1. Those that occurred before the moment of speech;

2. Those that coincide with the moment of speech;

3. Those that will occur after the moment of speech.

These three temporal meanings are expressed through specific verb forms [5, p. 118].

Sequence of tenses is the temporal agreement of the verb in the subordinate clause with the verb of the main clause. In English, the tense of the verb in the subordinate clause depends on the tense of the main clause verb. Therefore, the rules for using tenses in subordinate clauses according to the tense of the main clause verb are called sequence of tenses.

If the main clause verb is in the past tense, demonstrative pronouns and temporal adverbs change when converting from direct speech to reported speech: here – there, this – that, these – those, now – then, at that time (moment), today – that day, yesterday – the day before, on the previous day, ago – before, a year ago – a year before, last night – previous night, tomorrow – the next day, the day after tomorrow – two days later, the day before yesterday – two days before, next year – the next year, the following year. For example:

“Because he came here the most times,” the old man said [7, p. 24]. – Барои он ки ӯ ба инҷо зиёд меомад, – гуфт пирамард.

The old man said that he had come there the most times [7, p. 26]. – Пирамард гуфт, ки ӯ ба онҷо зиёд меомад.

The past tense of a verb, regardless of all its grammatical forms and variations, denotes an action that occurred before the moment of speech, that is, the speaker talks about a completed action and other processes. If the verb in the main clause is in the past tense (Past Indefinite Tense), according to the rule of sequence of tenses, the verb in the reported clause changes to another tense. According to this rule:

Present Indefinite → Past Indefinite

Present Continuous → Past Continuous

Present Perfect → Past Perfect

Present Perfect Continuous → Past Perfect Continuous

Furthermore, the tenses Past Indefinite Tense and Past Continuous Tense can change to Past Perfect Tense and Past Perfect Continuous Tense; the Future Indefinite Tense, Future Continuous Tense, and Future Perfect Tense change to Future in the Past Tense. Examples are provided below to illustrate this.

1. Present Indefinite → Past Indefinite

"I know," the old man said. "It is quite normal" [7, p. 8]. – Медонам, – гуфт пирамард. – Бояд ҳамин тавр бошад.

The old man said that he knew and it was quite normal [7, p. 18]. – Пирамард гуфт, ки ӯ медонад ва бояд ҳамин тавр бошад.

Although the subordinate verb in reported speech is in the past (knew), in Tajik translation it retains the present meaning (медонад).

2. Present Continuous → Past Continuous

"He's coming up," he said [7, p. 78]. – Боло мебарояд, – гуфт ӯ.

He said that he was coming up. – Ӯ гуфт, ки ӯ боло баромада истодааст.

3. Present Perfect → Past Perfect

The Past Perfect in Tajik corresponds to the remote past. It is formed from the main verb's past participle plus the past tense of the auxiliary verb. Its main uses:

a) To express a past action that occurred at a distant time.

b) To denote an action completed before another past action.

"He's got something," the old man said aloud [7, p. 38]. – Чизе ёфт, – гуфт пирамард бо овоз баланд.

The old man said aloud that he had got something [7, p. 42]. – Пирамард бо овози баланд гуфт, ки вай чизе ёфтааст.

4. Present Perfect Continuous → Past Perfect Continuous

This corresponds to the remote past continuous in Tajik. It expresses an action that continued up to another past action, sometimes interrupted by another past action.

"I've been asking you to," the boy told him gently [7, p. 22]. – Ман туро интизорам, – гуфт писарак оромона.

The boy told him gently that he had been asking him to [7, p. 28]. – Писарак оромона гуфт, ки ӯ вайро интизор аст.

5. Past Indefinite / Past Continuous → Past Perfect / Past Perfect Continuous

"You bought me a beer," the old man said [7, p. 10]. – Ту ба ман оби чав харидӣ, – гуфт пирамард.

The old man said that he had bought him a beer [7, p. 15]. – Пирамард гуфт, ки вай ба ӯ оби чав харидааст.

6. Future tenses → Future in the Past

"I'll show them that I'm an honest woman," said my mother [9, p. 22]. – Ман ба онҳо нишон медиҳам, ки ман як зани росткор ҳастам, – гуфт модарам.

My mother said that she would show them that she is an honest woman [9, p. 100]. – Модарам гуфт, ки ӯ ба онҳо зани росткор буданаширо нишон медиҳад.

In English, besides Past Indefinite (past), Present Indefinite (present), and Future Indefinite (future), there is also Future in the Past, which has no exact equivalent in Tajik. It expresses an action that will occur after a past moment.

Examples:

a) She said, "We'll be dancing at 8 o'clock." – Ӯ гуфт: "Мо дар соати ҳашт рақсу бозӣ карда меистем."

She said that they would be dancing at 8 o'clock. – Ӯ гуфт, ки онҳо дар соати ҳашт рақсу бозӣ карда меистанд.

b) My sister said: "I'll have finished my home task by the evening." – Хоҳарам гуфт: "Ман супориши хонагиамро то бегоҳӣ иҷро карда мешавам."

My sister said that she would have finished her home task by the evening. – Хоҳарам гуфт, ки ӯ супориши хонагиашро то бегоҳӣ иҷро карда мешавад.

c) He said: "I'll have been fixing my car since early morning." – Ӯ гуфт: "Ман мошинамро аз саҳарӣ барвақт боз таъмир карда меистам."

He said that he would have been fixing his car since early morning. – *Ū* гуфт, ки *ӯ* аз сахарӣ барвақт боз мошинашро таъмир карда меистад.

In English, the verb in the main clause, in addition to the past tense, can also be expressed in the present, future, and perfect tenses. The present tense of the verb indicates an action that is ongoing at the moment of speech. The future tense denotes an action that will occur after the moment of the speaker's utterance. The perfect tenses in English are used to express an action that has been completed by the present time and whose result is known.

If the verb in the main clause is in one of the tenses Present Indefinite, Present Perfect, or Future Indefinite, the verb in the reported clause remains in the same tense as in the direct speech; that is, it does not change when transforming direct speech into reported speech. In addition, demonstrative pronouns and adverbs of time and place remain unchanged in reported speech. The following examples illustrate this:

1. She says : I can't translate this article. - *Ū* мегӯяд: Ман ин мақоларо тарҷума карда наметавонам.

She says that she can't translate this article. – *Ū* мегӯяд, ки *ӯ* ин мақоларо тарҷума карда наметавонад.

2. Peter says: We have six lessons tomorrow and all the subjects are difficult. – Пётр мегӯяд: Мо фардо шаш соат дарс дорем ва ҳамаи фанҳо мушкил мебошанд.

Peter says that they will have six lessons tomorrow and all the subjects are difficult. – Пётр мегӯяд, ки онҳо фардо шаш соат дарс доранд ва ҳамаи фанҳо мушкил мебошанд [1, p. 291].

3. Peter says to Bob: I hate to break the news, but our sales were down again last month [1, p. 11]. – Пётр ба Боб мегӯяд: Ман хабаркаширо бад мебинам, аммо моҳи гузашта савдои мо боз барбод рафт.

Peter tells Bob that he hates to break the news, but their sales were down again last month. – Пётр ба Боб мегӯяд, ки *ӯ* хабаркаширо бад мебинад, аммо моҳи гузашта савдои онҳо барбод рафт.

From the examples provided, it is clear that demonstrative pronouns and adverbs of time and place, including the pronoun “this – ин” and the adverbs “tomorrow – пагоҳ” and “last – гузашта,” remain the same in both direct and reported speech. The reason for this is that, according to the rule of sequence of tenses, when the verb in the main clause is in the present tense, the noted pronouns and adverbs do not change in reported speech [4, c. 128].

A study of literary works has revealed that, in most cases, the verb in the main clause of reported speech is in the past tense. However, instances where the verb in reported speech is in the present, present perfect, or future tense are rare. Although these forms are noted in scholarly literature, they are hardly ever found in the literary works that were studied.

1. She says (has said, will say) that she is cleaning the room now. - *Ū* мегӯяд (гуфт, мегӯяд), ки *ӯ* ҳоло хучраро тоза карда истодааст.

2. He says (has said, will say) that he has just written a letter. - *Ū* мегӯяд (гуфт, мегӯяд) Ӯ хоҳад гуфт), ки *ӯ* ҳозиракак мактуб навиштааст.

From the following examples, it can be seen that if the verb in the main clause is in one of these tenses - present, present perfect, or future - the verb in the reported clause does not change its tense form. Therefore, when translating into Tajik, these English examples are rendered directly, without altering the tense of the verb. Thus, in reported speech where the verb is in one of these tenses - Present Indefinite, Present Perfect, or Future Indefinite - no significant changes are observed compared to a main clause whose verb is in the past tense (Past Indefinite). Consequently, when converting such types of sentences, no major difficulties arise.

The verb plays a central role in expressing temporal, aspectual, and modal meanings in English. Its forms allow speakers to indicate the timing, duration, and nature of an action or state, making verbs essential for clear communication. English verbs are expressed in three main tenses—past, present, and future—each corresponding to actions occurring before, during, or after the moment of speech. These

temporal distinctions are realized through specific verb forms, which are crucial in both direct and reported speech. The tense of a verb in a subordinate clause depends on the tense of the main clause. When the main clause verb is in the past tense, verbs in the subordinate clause usually shift to a corresponding past form, and demonstrative pronouns and temporal adverbs often change. Conversely, if the main clause verb is in the present or future tense, the subordinate clause verb generally retains its original tense, and pronouns and adverbs remain unchanged.

Conclusion

In summary, mastery of English verb tenses and the sequence of tenses is fundamental for accurate communication, translation, and interpretation of both spoken and written texts. Correctly applying tense transformations in reported speech allows learners to convey the precise timing of actions and maintain the original meaning of statements. The study of these grammatical patterns enhances both linguistic competence and practical translation skills, highlighting the importance of verbs in the English language.

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